

Appendix of the paper

“A Systematic Literature Review on Counterexample Explanation”

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1. Overview

This appendix contains a bibliography of all primary studies that we have analyzed in our systematic literature review, provides an overview of the data items we extracted from these studies (Section 2) and tabulates the primary studies for each data item we extracted (Section 3). For the latter, the data items are grouped by research questions.

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2. Data Items

The following table lists and describes the data items that we extracted from the primary studies, and further maps them to the research questions.

Table 1: Extracted data items.

ID	Item	RQs	Description
F1	Different types of counterexample representations	RQ1	The way counterexample is represented for improving the interpretation. Different types of counterexample explanations are graphical, textual, tabular, and trace representation.
F2	Statements on representing a counterexample	RQ1	Qualitative statements that describe the uniqueness or advantages of the representation.
F3	Different types of processed counterexamples	RQ2	The way counterexample is processed and generates either a modified trace of counterexample or an additional trace in addition to the counterexample for improving the interpretation. Different types of processed counterexamples are minimized counterexample, witness and counterexample, and multiple counterexample.
F4	Statements on processed counterexample	RQ2	Qualitative statements that describe the uniqueness or advantages of the processed counterexample.
F5	Categorizing minimized counterexample studies based on specifications	RQ2	The minimized counterexample studies are categorized based on the kind of specification and verification model. Categories are qualitative, real-time, and probabilistic.
F6	Methods used to minimize a counterexample	RQ2	The methods used to minimize a counterexample are collected and clustered. Methods found are search, translation and abstraction, and comparison with correct system behavior.
F7	Additional information to enrich the counterexample explanation	RQ3	In addition to the counterexample explanation, more information is provided to improve the interpretation.
F8	Statements on processed counterexample	RQ3	Qualitative statements that describe the uniqueness or advantages of the additional information.
F9	Input domain (system and requirement specification)	RQ4	Collects the different design models used as input domain. If no design model is found, we consider the verification model as the input domain.

Table 1 continued from previous page

ID	Item	RQs	Description
F10	Output domain (counterexample explanation)	RQ4	Collects the different output domains used to explain the counterexample. If the final output is a trace, then we didn't consider for this research question.
F11	Relations between input and output domains	RQ4	We categorize the relation of counterexample explanation to the input domain as whether the counterexample represented is either the same or different from the user-provided input domain. Further, we identify whether the counterexample is represented as simulation in the given input or reference/mapping to the given input domain.
F12	Temporal logic	RQ5	Collects the different temporal logics used for counterexample explanation.
F13	Property types	RQ5	Collects the different specification properties used for counterexample explanation.
F14	Verification tools	RQ6	Collects the different verification tools used for counterexample explanation.
F15	Frameworks	RQ6	Collects the different frameworks used for counterexample explanation.
F16	Statements on frameworks or model checkers	RQ6	Qualitative statements that describe the uniqueness or advantages of the framework or model checker.
F17	Application domain	RQ7	Collects the different application domains used for counterexample explanation.
F18	Application types	RQ7	Collects the different applications (e.g, industrial, realworld) used for counterexample explanation.
F19	Evaluation aspects	RQ7	Collects the different evaluation aspects used for counterexample explanation.
F20	Evaluation methods	RQ7	Collects the different evaluation methods used for counterexample explanation.

3. List of primary studies

This section complements Section 5 of the systematic literature review that describes the results of the review. Particularly, it tabulates the primary studies for the categories we used for the quantitative data items. The data items are grouped by the seven research questions of our study.

3.1. *RQ1: How are counterexamples explained and what are the effects of this explanation on counterexample interpretation?*

Table 2: Different types of counterexample representations (F1).

Types of counterexample representations	Primary studies	Count
Graphical Representation	[1–54]	54
Trace	[55–89]	35
Textual Representation	[90–106]	17
Graphical Representation and Tabular View	[107–111]	5
Tabular View	[112–116]	5
Total count	116	

3.2. *RQ2: How are counterexamples processed and what effect does it have on interpreting the counterexample?*

Table 3: Different types of processed counterexample (F3).

Processed counterexample	Primary studies	Count
Minimized counterexample	[2, 7, 28–30, 39, 43, 45, 51, 54–56, 58, 59, 61–66, 68–70, 72–76, 79–81, 83–88, 95]	38
Witness and Counterexample	[11, 21, 40, 57, 67, 71, 77, 89, 105]	9
Multiple Counterexample	[38, 46, 53, 60, 78, 102, 104]	7
N/A	[1, 3–6, 8–10, 12–20, 22–27, 31–37, 41, 42, 44, 47–50, 52, 82, 90–94, 96–101, 103, 106–116]	62
Total count	116	

Table 4: Categorizing minimized counterexample studies based on specifications (F5).

Categories	Primary studies	Count
Qualitative	[2, 28–30, 45, 55, 56, 58, 59, 62–66, 68, 69, 73, 74, 79, 80, 83–88, 95]	27
Probabilistic	[39, 43, 51, 54, 61, 70, 72, 75, 76, 81]	10
Real-time	[7]	1
N/A	[1, 3–6, 8–27, 31–38, 40–42, 44, 46–50, 52, 53, 57, 60, 67, 71, 77, 78, 82, 89–94, 96–116]	78
Total count	116	

Table 5: Methods used to minimize a counterexample (F6).

Methods	Primary studies	Count
Search	[2, 39, 51, 55, 56, 61–66, 69, 74, 87]	14
Translation and abstraction	[7, 70, 72, 75, 95]	5
Comparison with correct system behavior	[29, 30, 86, 88]	4
A specific or adapt an existing algorithm	[28, 43, 45, 54, 58, 59, 68, 73, 76, 79–81, 83–85]	15
N/A	[1, 3–6, 8–27, 31–38, 40–42, 44, 46–50, 52, 53, 57, 60, 67, 71, 77, 78, 82, 89–94, 96–116]	78
Total count	116	

3.3. *RQ3: What kind of additional information is used to enrich the counterexample explanation?*

Table 6: Additional information to enrich the counterexample explanation (F7).

Categories	Primary studies	Count
Additional information along with graphical representation	[1, 14, 52]	3
Additional information along with textual representation	[90–92, 96, 112]	5
N/A	[2–13, 15–51, 53–89, 93–95, 97–111, 113–116]	108
Total count	116	

3.4. *RQ4: For which input domains are the counterexample explanation approaches available? What is the influence of the input domain on the explanation?*

Table 7: Input domain (F9).

Input domain	Primary studies	Count
System model (State machine/Kripke/MDP/DTM-C/LTS)	[5, 6, 10–12, 19, 24, 29–32, 34, 38–40, 42, 43, 45–52, 54, 93, 97, 100, 104, 108, 110, 113, 115, 116]	35
Programming Language	[2, 21, 25, 26, 28, 41, 44, 99, 101–103, 105, 106, 109, 114]	15
Function Block Diagram	[1, 8, 13, 16, 17, 36, 37]	7
Structured English Language	[91, 92, 96, 98]	4
Component diagram	[3, 7, 18, 111]	4
Graph	[22]	1
Others	[4, 9, 14, 15, 20, 23, 27, 33, 35, 53, 90, 94, 95, 107, 112]	15
N/A (Trace representation)	[55–89]	35
Total count	116	

Table 8: Output domain (F10).

Output domain	Primary studies	Count
Programming Language	[101–103, 105, 106]	5
Function Block Diagram	[1, 13, 16, 17, 36, 37]	6
Structured English Language	[91, 92, 96–98]	5
Component Diagram	[7, 18]	2
Graph	[21, 22, 29–32, 39, 41–46]	13
Fault tree	[34, 47–51, 54]	7
Others	[2–6, 8–12, 15, 19, 20, 24–28, 33, 35, 38, 40, 52, 53, 90, 93, 99, 100, 104, 107–116]	43
N/A (Trace representation)	[14, 23, 55–89, 94, 95]	35
Total count	116	

Table 9: Relations between input and output domains (F11).

Category	Sub-category	Primary studies	Count
Independent	Simulation	[12, 15, 25]	3
	Reference/Mapping	-	-
	Traceability	[3, 6, 8, 22, 28, 38, 39, 45–48, 50, 51, 54, 90–92, 95–98, 100, 112]	23
	No Reference/Mapping	[2, 5, 10, 11, 19–21, 24, 26, 29–35, 40–44, 49, 52, 53, 93, 99, 104, 108–110, 113–116]	34
Same	Simulation	[1, 13, 16–18, 36, 37, 107, 111]	9
	Reference/Mapping	[4, 7, 9, 14, 23, 27, 94, 101–103, 105, 106]	12
	Traceability	-	-
	No Reference/Mapping	-	-
N/A (Trace representation)		[14, 23, 55–89, 94, 95]	35
Total count			116

3.5. *RQ5: What are the different temporal logics used to express system specifications and what type of properties are covered in counterexample explanation approaches?*

Table 10: Temporal logic (F12).

Temporal logic	Primary studies	Count
LTL	[1, 2, 6, 17–19, 24–27, 36, 37, 48, 52, 53, 55, 56, 58, 62, 63, 65, 67, 71, 74, 78, 83, 88, 100, 105–107]	31
CTL	[8, 11, 20, 38, 40, 85, 87, 109, 110, 115]	10
PCTL	[39, 75, 76, 81, 93]	5
CSL	[47, 49, 50, 54]	4
LTL, CTL	[13, 113, 114]	3
μ -calculus	[22, 41]	2
ACTL	[60, 80]	2
CL	[82, 95]	2
PSL	[10, 84]	2
Others	[3, 7, 9, 42, 45, 46, 57, 61, 91, 98]	10
Unknown/not specific	[4, 5, 12, 14–16, 21, 23, 28–35, 43, 44, 51, 59, 64, 66, 68–70, 72, 73, 77, 79, 86, 89, 90, 92, 94, 96, 97, 99, 101–104, 108, 111, 112, 116]	45
Total count	116	

Table 11: Property types (F13).

Property types	Primary studies	Count
Safety, Liveness	[1, 2, 4, 7, 8, 19, 20, 30, 37, 41, 44, 48, 52, 53, 57, 58, 62, 74, 89]	19
Safety	[17, 21, 28, 29, 38, 61, 63, 67, 68, 73, 77, 102, 104, 105]	14
Liveness	[10, 26, 83, 86]	4
Unknown/not specific	[3, 5, 6, 9, 11–16, 18, 22–25, 27, 31–36, 39, 40, 42, 43, 45–47, 49– 51, 54–56, 59, 60, 64–66, 69–72, 75, 76, 78–82, 84, 85, 87, 88, 90– 101, 103, 106–116]	79
Total count	116	

3.6. RQ6: Which verification tools and frameworks are developed and used to explain counterexamples, and how do they effect the counterexample explanation?

Table 12: Verification tools (F14).

Verification tool	Primary studies	Count
NuSMV/SMV/nuXmv	[1, 3, 13, 15–18, 27, 36, 37, 40, 45, 46, 58, 60, 67, 73, 78, 80, 84, 88, 107, 108, 110–116]	31
PRISM	[43, 47, 49–51, 54, 61, 70, 72, 75, 76, 81, 93, 97]	15
SPIN	[6, 15, 19, 49, 51, 55, 56, 62, 64, 74, 104]	12
Maude	[2, 12, 24–26]	5
ACL2	[90–92, 96]	4
VIS	[11, 20, 59, 109]	4
Others	[10, 14, 21, 22, 29–34, 38, 42, 48, 54, 57, 63, 72, 76, 79, 85, 86, 89, 95, 99–103, 105, 106, 114, 116]	27
Unknown/not specific	[4, 23, 28, 39, 41, 44, 52, 53, 65, 66, 69, 71, 77, 82, 83, 87, 94, 98]	18
Total count	116	

Table 13: Frameworks (F15).

Framework	Reference	URL	Count
DiPro	[43, 54, 81, 93]	http://www.uni-konstanz.de/soft/dipro/download.php	4
MODCHK	[1, 13, 17, 37]	https://github.com/igor-buzhinsky/nusmv_counterexample_visualizer	4
ASSERT	[90-92, 96]	-	4
AutoFocus3	[3, 18, 111]	https://www.fortiss.org/veroeffentlichungen/software/autofocus-3	3
SpinCause	[48, 49, 51]	http://www.uni-konstanz.de/soft//tools/spincause/	3
KEGVis	[38, 40, 42]	http://www.drawsvg.org/	3
CLEAR	[29, 30]	https://github.com/gbarbon/clear/	2
A2G2V	[31, 32]	-	2
IFADIS	[108, 115]	-	2
STANCE	[14, 23]	-	2
FaultCAT, CX2FT	[47, 50]	-	2
SMART	[85, 87]	-	2
FRET	[33]	https://github.com/NASA-SW-VnV/fret	1
RailComplete	[98]	https://www.railcomplete.com/en/downloads/	1
IBM RoseRT	[10]	https://www.ibm.com/docs/en/rtr	1
Ivy	[5]	https://www.cs.tau.ac.il/~odedp/ivy/	1
COMICS	[39]	https://www-i2.informatik.rwth-aachen.de/i2/comics/	1
DSValidator	[99]	https://ssvlab.github.io/dsverifier/dsvalidator/index.html	1
FASTEN	[107]	https://sites.google.com/site/fastenroot/	1
PLCverif	[114]	https://readthedocs.web.cern.ch/display/ICKB/PLCverif/	1
PyNuSMV	[46]	https://pypi.org/project/pynusmv/	1
VIS	[109]	https://ptolemy.berkeley.edu/projects/embedded/research/vis/	1

AMASE	[4]	https://github.com/afrl-rq/OpenAMASE/wiki/About-AMASE	1
Arcade.PLC	[28]	https://arcade.embedded.rwth-aachen.de/doku.php?id=arcade.plc	1
[Mc]SQUARE	[77]	https://arcade.embedded.rwth-aachen.de/	1
RuleBase PE	[52]	http://www.research.ibm.com/haifa/Workshops/rulebase2010/index.shtml	1
MechatronicUML	[7]	http://www.mechatronicuml.org/en/index.html	1
ELARVA	[82]	http://www.cs.um.edu.mt/svrg/Tools/ELARVApplus/	1
NuSeen	[113]	http://nuseen.sourceforge.net/	1
SpinRCP	[19]	http://lms.uni-mb.si/spinrcp/	1
FLAVERS/Ada	[69]	http://laserweb.cs.umass.edu/verification-examples/chiron/original/2a2e/source/ada_flavors/index.html	1
GraphML	[21]	http://graphml.graphdrawing.org/	1
OERITTE	[36]	https://github.com/ShakeAnApple/cxbacktracker/	1
AnaCon	[95]	-	1
Pseudo-merge	[22]	-	1
EOFM	[100]	-	1
ProofProd	[71]	-	1
Evidence Explorer	[41]	-	1
Alfi	[78]	-	1
Theseus	[15]	-	1
MACEMC	[44]	-	1
QuantUM	[34]		1
ATL	[35]		1

Unknown/not specific	[2, 6, 8, 9, 11, 12, 16, 20, 24–27, 45, 53, 55–68, 70, 72–76, 79, 80, 83, 84, 86, 88, 89, 94, 97, 101–106, 110, 112, 116]	-	52
Total count			116

3.7. RQ7: How are counterexample explanation approaches evaluated?

Table 14: Application domain (F17).

Application domain	Primary studies	Count
Protocol	[2, 5, 25, 26, 32, 39, 44, 62, 70, 72, 74–76, 85]	14
Hardware	[11, 15, 28, 36, 43, 50, 53, 73, 79, 81, 93, 104, 110, 114]	14
Automotive	[20, 23, 34, 35, 42, 47, 51, 54, 78, 88]	10
Robotics	[4, 8, 18, 45, 97, 99]	6
Avionics	[89–92, 96]	5
Nuclear	[1, 13, 17, 37]	4
Railway	[94, 98, 112]	3
Others	[6, 7, 9, 12, 14, 27, 41, 48, 49, 63, 95, 105, 111]	13
Unknown/not specific	[10, 21, 22, 29–31, 52, 55, 57–59, 61, 64, 65, 67–69, 77, 80, 82, 84, 86, 87, 101, 102, 106–108]	28
N/A	[3, 16, 19, 24, 33, 38, 40, 46, 56, 60, 66, 71, 83, 100, 103, 109, 113, 115, 116]	19
Total count	116	

Table 15: Application types (F18).

Application type	Primary studies	Count
Reference to non-industrial application	[5, 22, 25, 26, 29, 30, 32, 39, 41, 43, 52, 57, 58, 62, 70, 72, 75, 76, 79, 81, 85–87, 90, 93, 99]	26
Reference to industrial application	[2, 8, 10–12, 21, 31, 36, 42, 44, 55, 73, 74, 77, 82, 101, 102]	17
Example application	[2, 8, 10–12, 21, 31, 36, 38, 42, 44, 55, 73, 74, 77, 82, 100–102]	17
Industrial application	[1, 6, 13–15, 17, 37, 45, 53, 91, 92, 96, 98, 111, 112]	15
Non-Industrial application	[4, 9, 18, 94, 95, 97]	6
Reference to industrial and non-industrial applications	[48, 49, 61, 78, 104]	5
Industrial and non-industrial applications	[50]	1
Unknown/not specific	[59, 64, 65, 67–69, 80, 84, 107, 108]	10
N/A	[3, 16, 19, 24, 33, 38, 40, 46, 56, 60, 66, 71, 83, 100, 103, 109, 113, 115, 116]	19
Total count	116	

Table 16: Evaluation aspects (F19).

Evaluation aspect	Primary studies	Count
Efficiency, Performance	[10, 11, 20, 28, 35, 39, 41, 42, 44, 45, 47–51, 55, 58, 59, 62, 67–69, 72–77, 80, 84, 85, 94, 99, 105]	34
Effectiveness	[1, 2, 4–9, 12–15, 17, 18, 22, 23, 25–27, 31, 32, 36, 54, 63, 81, 82, 86, 90–93, 95, 96, 101, 106–108, 110–112, 114]	41
Efficiency, Performance, and Scalability	[34, 52, 57, 61, 64, 65, 70, 78, 79, 89, 97, 102]	12
Efficiency, Performance, and Efficiency	[21, 29, 30, 37, 43, 53, 88, 98, 104]	9
Scalability and Effectiveness	[87]	1
N/A	[3, 16, 19, 24, 33, 38, 40, 46, 56, 60, 66, 71, 83, 100, 103, 109, 113, 115, 116]	19
Total count	116	

Table 17: Evaluation methods (F20).

Evaluation method	Primary studies	Count
Use-Case(s)	[1, 2, 4–10, 12–15, 17, 18, 20–23, 25–28, 31, 32, 34–37, 41, 43–45, 47–50, 52–54, 57, 58, 61, 63, 72, 75, 77–79, 81, 82, 86, 88–96, 98, 99, 101, 102, 104–106, 111, 114]	70
Benchmark and Use-Case(s)	[39, 42, 51, 62, 70, 73, 74, 76, 85, 87, 97]	11
Benchmark	[11, 55, 59, 64, 65, 67–69, 80, 84]	10
User-Study and Use-Case(s)	[29, 30, 110, 112]	4
User-Study	[107, 108]	2
N/A	[3, 16, 19, 24, 33, 38, 40, 46, 56, 60, 66, 71, 83, 100, 103, 109, 113, 115, 116]	19
Total count	116	

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Acronyms

ACL2 A Computational Logic for Applicative Common Lisp.

AMASE Aerospace Multi-agent Simulation Environment.

ASSERT Analysis of Semantic Specifications and Efficient generation of Requirements-based Tests.

BDD Binary Decision Diagrams.

BFL Brute Force Lifting.

BFS Breath-First Search.

BPMN Business Process Model and Notation.

Butramin BUg TRAcE MINimization.

CAD Computer-aided Design.

CBD Contract-Based Design.

CBMC C Bounded Model Checker.

CL Contract Language.

CLAN Contract Language ANalyser.

CNL Controlled/Constrained Natural Language.

COMICS Computing Minimal Counterexamples.

CSL Continuous Stochastic Logic.

CTL Computation Tree Logic.

CTMC Continuous-Time Markov Chain.

DFS Depth-First Search.

DiPro Directed Probabilistic Counterexample Generation Tool.

DSL Domain-Specific Language.

DTMC Discrete-Time Markov Chain.

FASTEN FormAl SpecificaTion ENvironment.

FMEA Failure Mode and Effect Analysis.

FTA Fault Tree Analysis.

GF Grammatical Framework.

GraphML Graph Markup Language.

GUI Graphical User Interface.

HAZOP Hazard and Operability.

KEGVis Kounterexample generator and visualizer.

LTL Linear Temporal Logic.

LTS Labelled Transition System.

MDP Markov Decision Processes.

MILP Mixed Integer Linear Programming.

MPS Meta Programming System.

MRMC Markov Reward Model Checker.

MSC Message Sequence Chart.

NuSMV New Symbolic Model Verifier.

PCTL Probabilistic Computation Tree Logic.

PLC Programmable Logic Controller.

PRISM Probabilistic Symbolic Model Checker.

PROMELA Process or Protocol Meta Language.

PSL Property Specification Language.

RAE Requirements Analysis Engine.

RTCTL Real Time Computation Tree Logic.

SAT Satisfiability.

SMT Satisfiability Modulo Theories.

SMV Symbolic Model Verifier.

SPIN Simple PROMELA Interpreter.

STANCE Structural Analysis of Counter-Examples.

SysML Systems Modeling Language.

TCTL Timed Computational Tree Logic.

UAV Unmanned Aerial Vehicle.

UML Unified Modeling Language.

VIS Verification Interacting with Synthesis.

XBF eXtended Best-First.

XChck Multi-valued Model-Checker.